

RESIDUAL IMPACT STRENGTH OF WOVEN GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE BEAMS WITH IMPACT-INDUCED DAMAGE

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Abstract

Sub-critical instrumented impact tests were used to introduce small damage in the upper layer of beams made of 32-ply NEMA/ASTM G-10 grade woven glass reinforced epoxy. When a second, destructive, impact load was applied to the upper (damaged) surface of the specimens, they showed no loss in strength. When the second impact was applied to the lower (undamaged) surface, the measured strength was considerably lower than strength of virgin specimens. The drop in residual strength is observed when the first impact energy exceeds 60% of the critical failure energy. The initial mode of failure of the damaged specimens is different from that of undamaged specimens.

Introduction

Widespread application of woven fiber-reinforced composites in structures has generated an increasing interest in their mechanical properties. Since the early eighties, much work has been done in modelling the elastic properties of woven fabrics [1-8]. However, much less progress has been achieved in studying their mechanisms of damage and fracture, particularly when compared to those of laminates with unidirectional plies [9,10]. The result is that there are no methods for estimating the material tolerance to impact-induced damage. Development of such methods and determination of the parameters governing the residual strength of woven composites after sub-critical impact loading is important for their design and safe use in structural applications.

Recently Robinson and Davies [11] reported the results of low-velocity impact tests on woven fabric glass/epoxy composite plates. It was found that impact at sub-critical energy resulted in visual damage on the upper and lower surfaces of the plate and a barely visual inner damage (BVID), detected by ultrasonic C-scanning. The extent of the damage was characterized by the maximum size of the damaged zone. It was established that, within the range of the mean flexural strain rates of 10^0 - 10^1 s^{-1} used in the experiments, the process could be considered quasi-static. The damage signature was determined by the impact energy, without separating the effects of the impactor mass and velocity. Based on a limited number of tests, an hypothesis was also proposed that the relationship between the peak contact force and the extent of the impact-induced damage was independent of the specimen's diameter.

Impact damage in woven composites can take many forms: matrix cracking, fiber pull-out and fracture in regions of tensile stresses and debonding and microbuckling of fibers under compressive stresses [8,12-15]. In their study of plates, Robinson and Davies [11] found damage resulting from compression near the upper surface and damage resulting from tension near the lower surface. This made it difficult to separate the effect of each damage type on the residual properties of the woven laminate. In our tests of beams, we found that it was possible to inflict damage of one type near the upper surface of the specimen, without causing damage to the lower surface. Thus it became possible to study the effect of a particular mode of impact damage on the residual impact strength.

In this work, the effect of impact-induced damage in woven glass/epoxy composite beams, on their resistance to a second impact loading is examined. In particular, we are interested in the damage in the vicinity of the contact area between impactor and specimen, on the upper surface of the three point bending specimen, where the state of stress is mostly compression. Previous studies [16] have shown that the material is insensitive to repeated impacts on the upper surface. Therefore it was decided to study the residual strength after first damage in the upper surface, by reversing the direction of the second impact. After the initial, visual, damage is developed by the first impact, the specimen is turned upside down so that the damage is now at the lower face. When the subsequent, destructive, impact is applied, the initial damaged zone is loaded in tension. This is different from other studies of repeated impact loading, which are normally conducted on the same face of the specimen [17]. The use of beams as the test coupons allows to reveal the sensitivity of the woven material to the first damage created by lateral impact .

Experimental

The material used for this investigation is industrial NEMA/ASTM G-10 grade E-glass/Epoxy, containing 32 plies of woven fabric. The specimens, 6.3 ± 0.3 mm thick and 7.85 ± 0.3 mm wide, are cut in the warp direction with length varying from 40 mm to 120 mm. The in-plane mechanical properties of the material as given by [15] agree with our own tests.

The test configuration is a three-point bending (simply supported), where the impact load is applied at the center of the beam by a 1.48 kg falling dart having a cylindrical tip with a radius of 9 mm. The test arrangement and details of the data reduction are given in [16].

The tests were divided to four groups, using the same experimental setup. In the first group specimens of length from 40 mm to 120 mm were subjected to a single impact that caused total fracture. Many preliminary tests had to be run in order to establish the critical kinetic energy that the falling dart must have to break a specimen for every given length. This energy is denoted by U_{th} (for 'threshold energy').

The second group consisted of 50 and 100 mm long specimens, each one subjected to a single sub-critical impact U ($U < U_{th}$) of a different magnitude. These impacts caused no visual damage to the lower surface of the beams, but the upper surface showed clearly some internal damage on both sides of the contact zone (Fig. 1).

The third group consisted of the same specimens as in the second. After the first impact of each specimen, it was repeatedly impacted on for a few times, on the same surface as the first impact, by increasing the kinetic energy of the falling dart. There was no reduction in strength and the specimens failed when the applied energy reached the threshold value (U_{th}) of the virgin material.

Figure 1. Damaged upper surface, from sub-critical impact: (a) $U/U_{th}=0.95$, (b) $U/U_{th}=0.70$

The fourth group consisted of specimens that participated in the tests of the second group. After the first impact, the specimens were turned upside down so that the damaged surface was on their lower side and the repeated, second impact was applied to the undamaged surface. Originally the applied energy level in the second impact was lower than U_{th} and the result was that some specimens fractured and some did not. Having established that the residual strength in this sequence of loading was lower than the strength of virgin specimens, the level of the applied impact energy in the repeated impact was selected to be equal to U_{th} . This assured that the second impact would always cause fracture of the beam and the strength of the damaged specimen could be determined from the data recorded during the test [16]. It should be mentioned here that the energy stored in the beam at onset of fracture (to be denoted by U_f), is lower than the applied kinetic energy, and does not depend on its level.

Finally, a few tests were conducted with virgin specimens that had a small (0.5x0.5 mm) notch cut in the middle of their lower surface. A single destructive impact was applied in order to compare the mode of fracture to that of the damaged specimens.

Results and discussion

A typical load-time curve from a destructive impact test on an undamaged 100 mm long specimen is presented in Fig. 2(a). The catastrophic failure occurs when the contact force has reached its peak value (F_f) and is characterized by a sharp drop of the force, typical to a brittle fracture. The failure occurs by a transverse crack, originating in the middle of the beam at its lower face, that propagates perpendicular to the beam's axis. When the applied impact energy is higher than the threshold energy U_{th} , the normal crack continues to the upper surface, splitting the specimen in half. At threshold value, the crack deviates from its normal course at some distance from the lower surface and is arrested by the formation of delamination, as shown in Fig. 3(a).

A second, useful way to present impact data is by plotting the applied energy as a function of the contact force on the beam. The applied energy is calculated by integrating the force applied to the beam along the deflection. The fracture energy (U_f) is the energy stored in the beam when a sudden drop in the force is observed (Fig. 4(a)). The sudden drop in the force, with almost no change in the energy, is typical to the brittle failure observed in virgin specimens, when subjected to impact energy U_{th} or above. The value of the threshold energy U_{th} is 15-20% higher than the fracture energy U_f .

Figure 2. Typical load-time curves for 100 mm long specimens in destructive impact tests: (a) virgin specimen, (b) repeated impact on undamaged face of a damaged specimen.

Figure 3. Micrograph of 100 mm long specimens after impact failure: (a) virgin, (b) repeated impact on undamaged face of a damaged specimen, (c) specimen with notch at bottom.

The effect of specimen's length was examined by running a series of destructive impact tests on specimens of lengths from 40 to 120 mm. The mode of failure of all the specimens was identical to the brittle mode of the 100 mm specimens. When the results of the contact force at failure (F_f), normalized with respect to the corresponding beam's width, are plotted vs. the inverse beam's length (L), they form a straight line (Fig. 5), as predicted by classical beam theory. The tensile stress at failure is

$$\sigma_f = \left(\frac{F_f}{b} \right) \frac{3L}{2h^2} \tag{1}$$

where b and h are the beam's width and thickness respectively, which gives a value of 460 MPa. This value exceeds the quasi-static tensile strength of the material (331 MPa), as a result of strain rate dependence and due to the different nature of tensile and bending tests. The values of the threshold energy per 1 mm specimen's width for 50 and 100 mm long beams are 0.39 and 0.53 J/mm respectively.

Figure 4. Applied energy vs. load in destructive tests of 100 mm long specimens : (a) virgin specimen, (b) repeated impact on undamaged face of a damaged specimen.

Figure 5. Normalized critical contact force vs. inverse specimen length.

Having established the values of threshold energy as a function of beam's length, non-destructive impacts with energy levels lower than U_{th} were applied to 100 and 50 mm long beams. It was observed that the damage inflicted in such impacts was confined to the upper layer of the

specimen, just below the surface, on both sides of the contact area. When the impact energy is high (about 0.9 times U_{th}), the damage has a form of two white bands, approximately 2 mm apart, across the specimen's width as shown in Fig. 1(a). When the impact energy is lower, the bands are diluted and the individual damage spots become visible (Fig. 1(b)). Occasionally, some spots are scattered a few mm away from the two bands. This type of damage becomes visible when the applied impact energy is approximately 0.65 times the threshold energy of the particular specimen. It was shown [15] that woven composite under compression failed by formation of multiple kink bands. The observed spots in our tests confirm this type of failure.

When a second impact load, with threshold energy U_{th} , was applied to the damaged beams on the damaged face, there was no reduction in original strength. However, when the damaged beam was turned upside down such that the second impact was applied to the undamaged face, the strength was considerably lower than the original as shown in Figs. 2(b) and 4(b).

The kinetic energy of the dart in the first impact of specimen (b), in Fig. 2, was 0.48 J/mm, equal to $0.90U_{th}$. The strength reduction of that specimen was 30%. First impacts of different magnitudes would lead to different reductions in original strength. This is shown for 50 and 100 mm long beams in Fig. 6, by plotting failure stress in a second impact vs. the kinetic energy of the dart in a first impact, normalized with respect to the appropriate U_{th} . By normalizing the kinetic energy, the curve in figure 6 becomes general and it represents the residual strength of beams of different lengths, when subjected to similar loading conditions. The drop in residual strength starts when the kinetic energy in the first impact exceeds 60% of U_{th} .

Figure 6. Residual strength of damaged specimens.

As mentioned previously, the kinetic energy of the dart in the second impact was equal to U_{th} (of the virgin specimens). This assured catastrophic failure. The mode of failure, however, was different than in failure of virgin specimens, as evident by comparing Fig. 3(a) and 3(b). The first shows the crack in a virgin specimen. In the second, the crack initiates at the damage band, at the lower surface of the specimen, and propagates upward at approximately 45° . At some stage it changes direction and may cause delamination, or continue upward to the upper surface. This feature of initially inclined crack propagation is typical to all the tests of the damaged specimens and is probably the result of stress concentration in the area of the damage band. To show the effect of stress concentration on the failure mode, some impact tests were run on virgin beams that

contained a rectangular 0.5x0.5 mm notch at the bottom. The crack started at the corner of the notch (Fig. 3(c)) and propagated upward at approximately 45° , similar to Fig. 3(b).

Conclusions

The main results of the experimental study, conducted with laminated beams from G-10 grade woven glass reinforced epoxy, are as follows:

1. Impact failure of virgin beams of various length can be predicted by the maximum tensile stress or maximum tensile strain criterion. Failure occurs by a crack that propagates normal to the lower surface of the beam.
2. Sub-critical impact load generates visual damage only on the top surface of the beam, on both sides of the contact zone. The damage is formed by small discrete white spots that stem from micro-buckling of fibers as a result of the in-plane compression stress. As the impact gets closer to the critical value, the white spots become dense and form two white bands across the specimen's width.
3. The near-surface damage is insensitive to repeated compressive stress, arising from repeated impact loads on the damaged surface.
4. The near-surface damage is sensitive to tensile stress, arising from repeated impact load on the undamaged surface. Fracture is developed by an inclined crack starting within the damaged region and propagating at an angle of about 45° to the lower surface of the specimen.
5. The residual impact strength starts to decrease when the applied impact energy, of the first impact, is larger than 60% of the threshold energy of a virgin specimen. A single curve of residual strength vs. normalized (first) impact energy can represent behavior of beams with different dimensions (length and width). This relationship is characteristic of the material tolerance to near-surface damage, induced by impact load.

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